

ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA POLYMERISATION OF CARBON FIBRES: IMPACT ON ADHESION TO POLYURETHANE ELASTOMER

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1 Summary

An atmospheric plasma polymerisation (APP) route to enhance the adhesion properties of carbon fibres to elastomeric matrix was developed. In order to examine the impact of APP of acrylonitrile precursor on carbon fibres in regards to different parameters, the surface chemistry and physical properties of the modified fibres together with micromechanical characterisation of adhesion behaviour of carbon fibre and elastomeric matrix were characterised. The surface hydrophilicity of the carbon fibres and fibre matrix compatibility were increased. The interfacial behaviour of APP modified carbon fibres and polyurethane elastomers showed significant improvement as result of the introduction of chemical functionalities to the carbon fibre surface.

2 Introduction

Elastomeric matrix power transmission belting are widely used in the automotive industry and industrial equipments. The belts transmitting mechanical power between shafts through either friction or a combination of friction and the engagement of formed teeth in pulley grooves. They rely to a great extent on the quality of the bonding between fibres and elastomers in order to function correctly, as the mechanical properties of the composite depend intrinsically on the interfacial properties [1]. The whole belt is made up from the polyurethane/rubber matrix reinforced by tension bearing cords which run through the middle of the belt with a fabric covering the teeth of the belt to strengthen and protect them from wear. Basically the cord is there to carry the load but also be flexible. So the cord was used to maintain belt tooth pitch, transmit torque via tension between pulleys and contribute to good dynamic behaviour of belts. In

order to get a compact drive component, which can be integrated with a lot of power in a small space and providing versatility to drive designers; a reduced width belt with high power transmission capacity, strength, flexibility and durability, chemical resistance, low elongation, and a wide operational temperature is required. Therefore, carbon fibres, compared to other reinforcements, with higher specific strength and modulus, better chemical resistance and dimensional stability [2], are ideal used for high performance power transmission belts.

However, poor adhesion between carbon fibres and elastomeric matrices, which leads to “belt tensile decay”, is the main problem of the current carbon belt system. Mechanical interlocking is known to be the main interaction between the fibres and the elastomeric matrix polymer as compared to chemical bonding. Therefore, the primary function of a fibre surface modification is to introduce more functional groups reacting with the elastomeric matrix to form more chemical bonding and then to create optimum adhesion at the fibre-matrix interphase. Atmospheric plasma polymerization with a stable and uniform plasma environment at atmospheric pressure allows carbon fibres to be treated uniformly and continuously [3, 4]. In this study, a continuous APP route for modifying the carbon fibres to achieve good adhesion to elastomeric matrix and therefore to enhance the load carrying capability and fatigue life of the carbon fibre/elastomer composite was employed.

3 Methodology

APP was performed on unsized PAN based carbon fibre in an Openair® plasma Technology system (Plasma Jet PFW10-PAD; Plasmatreat®, Steinhagen,

Germany). N₂ and Air were used as ionization and carrier gases, respectively. Precursors used for APP was acrylonitrile (99 % purity, Fluka, UK). Different APP treatment time and precursor dosing rates were investigated. The parameters of APP are shown in Table 1. In order to examine the influences of APP on carbon fibres and the interfacial interaction between fibre and elastomeric matrix, the surface and bulk properties characterisations of carbon fibres has been conducted, including dynamic contact angle, zeta-potential, BET surface area, XPS, single fibre tensile strength measurements, and micromechanical characterisation of adhesion behaviour of carbon fibre and elastomeric matrix has been characterised through single fibre pull-out tests on model composites, etc.

4 Results and discussion

The surface morphologies of carbon fibre were examined using the SEM (Fig.1). It showed that the surfaces of all APP treated carbon fibres had relatively smooth appearances with no apparent crenulations on the fibre surface.

It is well known that mechanical interlocking can be a major contribution to the measured practical adhesion. To quantify the influence the surface roughness of the fibres on the adhesion to matrix, the BET surface area A_s of the carbon and glass fibres was determined, as shown in Table 2. The surface area of APP treated carbon fibres with the lowest processing was higher by around 20% than untreated carbon fibres, but an increase to at least 5–10 m²/g is required to have any significant effect on practical adhesion. Therefore, the small changes in surface area of the carbon fibre are not expected to make for any mechanical interlocking between the fibres and the matrix [5, 6].

For the contact angles measured using the modified-Wilhemy method, significant increases in surface hydrophilicity and higher surface energies were observed for APP treated carbon fibres (Table 3). The water contact angle hysteresis, defined as the difference between θ_a and θ_r , for APP treated carbon fibres was much lower than the untreated carbon fibres, which indicates the surface of APP treated carbon fibres was more chemically homogenous.

The pH-dependent ζ -potential measurements of carbon fibres (Fig.2) were performed to characterise the acidic/basic characters of the fibres, as shown in

Fig.2. All the fibres showed a typical behaviour of solid containing acidic groups with the indication of low isoelectric point (i.e.p.), and the ζ -potential plateau in the alkaline region [7, 8] ($6 < \text{pH} < 10$). The low i.e.p. values were not experimentally accessible, provided the very high ionic strengths induced by low pH could cause the compression of electrochemical double layer. However, the low i.e.p. values can reflect that high acidic surface character and the existing surface groups have a low affinity to protons [9]. Among all the fibres, T700GC-APP-A has the lowest ζ -potential plateau, which resulted from more dissociable functional groups existing on fibre surface. The ζ -potential plateau values decreased as the processing speed increase which was corresponding to the trend of apparent IFSS between APP treated carbon fibres and polyurethane elastomer.

The apparent interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of APP treated carbon fibres with the longest treatment time to polyurethane elastomer significantly increased by around 100% compared to that of untreated carbon fibres (Table 4). With the same precursor dosing rate, the increase of processing speed can lead to the decrease of the apparent IFSS. Also, with the same treatment time, apparent IFSS was dropped marginally with the increase of precursor dosing rate.

The influence of APP treatment on the surface composition of carbon fibres was investigated by XPS (Table 6). As expected the oxygen and nitrogen content of APP treated carbon fibres were both significantly increased compared to the original unsized carbon fibres. With the same precursor doing rate, increasing processing speed led to little increase of nitrogen and oxygen content. On the contrary, with the same treatment time, higher precursor doing rate can dramatically increase the nitrogen and oxygen content. The deconvolution of the high resolution spectra of C 1s on the carbon fibres (Fig.3) provides information about the chemical environments (or oxidation state) of the elements present on their surfaces. The resulting deconvoluted peak assignment for the C 1s of the carbon fibre samples exhibited overlap between the C-O and C*-C \equiv N. With longer APP treatment time or higher precursor dosing rate, more C=O, C-O/C*-C \equiv N and COOR were introduced. With shorter APP treatment time, less polar functional groups were grafted onto the fibre surface.

The introduction of polar oxygen and nitrogen groups onto the surface of the fibres leads to an increase of the fibre surface energy as well as changes to the surface energy components. The increase in the carbon fibre surface energy should lead to better wettability of the fibres by the matrix and, therefore, to a more intimate contact between the phases. Meanwhile, these groups should lead to improved interaction between the fibre and the polyurethane elastomer, which was proved by the agreement with the trend of apparent IFSS values.

Single fibre tensile strength and modulus were not affected by APP treatment as shown in Table 5. The tensile strength of all carbon fibres had a length dependence due to the flaw-induced nature of fibre failure [10, 11], with the average strengths of all the carbon fibres decreased with increasing gauge length. On the contrary, the fibre modulus remained constant as expected with the increasing of gauge length since they were not affected by the flaws along the fibres but dominated by the fibre core structure.

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Table1. APP treatment parameters.

APP treatment Parameters	
Flow of Monomer (g/h)	50;150
Flow of Ionized Gas-N ₂ (L/h)	2000
Flow of Carrier Gas-Air (L/h)	300
Power Input (kW)	2.1
Speed of Treatment (m/min)	0.08; 0.8;1.4
Stand Off Distance (mm)	12
Primary Pressure (Bar)	6

Fig.1. SEM images before and after APP treated T700GC carbon fibres using different processing parameters.

Fig.2. Zeta (ζ) –Potential as function of pH of untreated/ APP modified carbon fibres with different processing parameters.

Table 2 BET surface areas A_s of carbon fibres and before and after APP treatment.

Fibre investigated	BET (m ² /g)
T700GC-As received (AR)	0.3693 ± 0.0014
T700GC-APP-A (AN_N2+Air_0.08m/min, 50g/h)	0.4546 ± 0.0033
T700GC-APP-B (AN_N2+Air_0.8m/min, 50g/h)	0.3469 ± 0.0048
T700GC-APP-C (AN_N2+Air_1.4m/min, 50g/h)	0.3196 ± 0.0054
T700GC-APP-D (AN_N2+Air_1.4m/min, 150g/h)	0.3611 ± 0.0016

Table 3 Dynamic water contact angles and surface free energies calculated using acid-base approach ($\gamma_s(AB)$) of untreated/ APP modified carbon fibres

Fibre investigated	θ_a (W) / °	θ_r (W) / °	$\Delta\theta$ (W)/ °	γ_s (AB)/ mN/m
T700GC-AR	68.7 ± 1.4	60.3 ± 0.7	8.4	40.9 ± 2.6
T700GC-APP-A	43.1 ± 2.7	39.7 ± 1.4	3.4	53.2 ± 2.5

Table 4 Interfacial shear strengths of plasma modified T700GC CFs with polyurethane elastomer

Fibre investigated	τ_{IFSS} / MPa
T700GC-AR	20.1 ± 3.0
T700GC-APP-A	39.9 ± 1.5
T700GC-APP-B	31.9 ± 1.2
T700GC-APP-C	33.8 ± 1.2
T700GC-APP-D	30.9 ± 1.1

Table 5 Tensile strength and Young's modulus at different gauge lengths of untreated/ APP modified carbon fibres

	Fibres	Gauge length / mm * (×25 samples)		
		20*	25*	30*
Tensile Strength / MPa	T700GC-AR	4066 ± 188	3946 ± 124	3829 ± 136
	T700GC-APP- A	4112 ± 186	3773 ± 222	3710 ± 262
Young's Modulus/ GPa	T700GC-AR	219 ± 2.5	239 ± 4.3	237 ± 5.4
	T700GC-APP- A	242 ± 5.0	248 ± 4.7	250 ± 3.1

Table 6 Surface composition (in at.%) of atmospheric plasma fluorinated carbon fibres determined by XPS

Investigated Fibres	O 1s / at.%	C 1s / at.%	N 1s / at.%
T700GC-AR	8.0	90.6	1.4
T700GC-APP-A	18.7	71.5	9.4
T700GC-APP-B	11.1	85.1	3.8
T700GC-APP-C	13.0	84.1	2.9
T700GC-APP-D	15.6	77.1	7.2

Fig.3. High resolution C 1s X-ray photoelectron spectra of T700GC PAN carbon fibres before and after APP modified carbon fibres with different processing parameters